

WAYS TO CONTROL POVERTY IN LESS DEVELOPED COUNTRIES

Poverty is a situation, a state in which an individual or community lives below the minimum standard of living that is to say when one can not meet the basic human needs. The international poverty line, currently set at 1.90 Dollars per day. Poverty may completely be hard to be eliminated but it can be controlled from increasing. These are some of the ways to control poverty in less developed countries;

Infrastructural development;

- (a) Infrastructure in form of transportation facilities, hospitals, schools, water supply pumps, communication facilities, construction of electricity power centers can speed up urbanization. This is the coming into existence of towns that encourage foreign investors to invest in not only urban areas but also in the rural areas. This in turn provides employment and helps in improving the standard of living of the people in such areas.
- (b) During the construction of infrastructure, jobs are created for engineers and other sectors in the economy. This may be in a direct form or indirect form which in turn improves on the tax base of the government, people's standard of living thus reducing the poverty levels.

Make education a priority; Educating the masses helps in creating a new class of elites and sharpens one's way of thinking. This can improve the levels of creativity, develop problem-solving skills, create a modern society that can compete favorably internationally. Educated individuals have higher chances of thriving even in countries with poor economies hence improving the standard of living of such individuals. This creates diversity since they have been exposed to different forms of education, some become engineers, teachers, doctors, and many more which in turn can reduce the crime rates in the society by the fact that most people are knowledgeable.

Diversify the economy; Instead of a country depending on a few sectors of the economy, they should support the developing sectors as well. This can be achieved through supporting several sectors like the fishing sector, forestry sector, agricultural sector, tourism sector, mining sector and many more which in turn can create jobs for the masses hence people will earn incomes and therefore improve on their standards of living thus reducing poverty.

Improve policy-making; Different policies determine the well-being of the economy, these may lead to a downfall or boost the economy.

- (a) National Minimum Wage; This policy is put up by the government and it is the least an employer can pay employees. The increase in the minimum by the government is an

effective way of increasing the incomes of the low-paid workers hence reducing wage inequality in an economy. Wage inequality is a situation in an economy where the poor are very poor and the rich are very rich. This policy protects workers from unduly low pay. However, this should be done under controlled measures because it may cause unemployment since firms may not be able to afford the workers therefore if it does cause unemployment, poverty could worsen.

(b) Government policies on investment; Government policies on investment can influence interest rates, these policies may include taxation. An increase in taxes may lead to a rise in the interest rates by the financial institutions hence discourage borrowing for investment however decrease in taxes may lead to a decrease in the interest rates by the financial institutions hence encourage borrowing for investment by the investors thus promoting economic growth thereby reducing poverty.

However, this should be done under controlled measures because the extreme increase of taxes can scare away investors and an extreme decrease of taxes may lead to inflation yet businesses can not thrive with the presence of inflation. Under controlled measures, the government may also put up tax holidays to encourage investment.

(c) Privatization policy; This is when government property is transferred to private property, it generally helps governments save money and increase efficiency since the private sector works towards profit maximization therefore the producer will work towards satisfying consumer needs at an affordable price hence it will improve on the standards of living of the public. Privatization also helps the government pay loans, control income inequality, reduce government expenses. Income inequality is controlled when the rich come up to buy government property hence reduces on their pool of funds at the same time controls inflation in an economy. Privatized companies tend to grow faster which in return creates more job opportunities for the masses thereby helping them earn an income that helps to improve the standards of living.

Control population Growth rate: Various methods have been used to control the population growth rate some of them may include educating the masses about the dangers of a high population, birth control methods, family planning methods. These can help reduce the stretches by both the national and family income hence improving the per capita income growth and well-being of the masses which in turn reduces the poverty levels.

Control Corruption: corruption is when government funds are used for personal benefits in form of fraud and embezzlement of funds which leads to misallocation and poor budgeting in an economy hence slows down growth. Strict monitoring and accountability of resources should be done and transparency in the allocation of government funds should be done to control corruption. Penalties should be given to individuals who perform fraud, this will encourage investment since the investor trust the government, and resources will be able to

reach minors these are the people in the rural areas hence increasing access to public services thus improving people's standards of living which controls the increase of poverty levels.

Encourage vocation education systems; As such the education system must be made more practical giving youths and the general population more hands-on work. This will in turn create more opportunities and increase craftsmanship which will create a way for self-employment creating more job creators than job seekers. This will help people earn income and thus improving their standards of living.

Encourage saving; Saving in banks can help in creating funds for borrowing which can be invested by those with insufficient funds. Money is withdrawn from the economy to help control income inequality and inflation which in turn encourages investment since business survives better in an economy with lower levels of inflation. Investment creates jobs which create income thus improving people's standards of living hence reducing the poverty levels

Promote political stability; Most politically unstable countries face a problem of political instabilities, this scare away potential investor because of fear to make losses due to policy changes, high cost of investment, however in a politically stable environment policies are stable and in case of any change voting is done making policies free and fair for the majority. This encourages investment which improves economic growth hence improving people's standards of living reducing poverty levels.

In conclusion, the above are some of the ways of controlling poverty in less developed areas. Other reasons may include encouraging small-scale investment, improving the land tenure system, and many more.